

ISSUES OF DEVELOPING LOGICAL COMPETENCE IN THE TRAINING OF MODERN PHYSICS TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the need, problems and solutions for developing students' logical competence based on a competency-based approach in the training of modern physics teachers. In addition, the article provides extensive information on the psychological and didactic aspects of developing the logical competence of future physics teachers, the state of development of the logical competence of future physics teachers in higher educational institutions, and the didactic importance of multimedia tools and information technologies in developing the logical competence of future physics teachers. Scientific conclusions and recommendations have been developed on the topic.*

Keywords: *effective solutions, development of logical competence, training of modern physics teachers, Analysis-synthesis, comparison, generalization, abstraction, classification, concretization, systematization, ability to apply the laws of formal logic in physics.*

INTRODUCTION

Innovative creative technologies for developing the logical competence of future physics teachers are being put into practice in world educational institutions. The International Education Concept until 2030, adopted by UNESCO and the European Union, and the “Future of Education and Skills 2030” project of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development are systematically working to improve the quality of education, develop the logical thinking skills of future teachers, which are a key component of educational activity, increase the effectiveness of lessons, and improve the criteria, factors, technologies, and models for developing students' logical competence.

In order to raise the quality of education to an international level, establish modular education, and improve the quality of professional training, scientific research is being conducted in world educational and research institutions to improve the competencies of future physics teachers such as abstracting scientific terms and quantities, drawing correct and quick conclusions based on logical thinking. Special attention is paid to scientific research on the development of logical competence of future physics teachers based on a competency-based approach using the laws of formal logic in teaching physics.

In our republic, normative foundations are being created to develop the logical thinking of future specialists, to improve the quality and efficiency of training specialists in the field of physics. “Increasing the level of coverage of young people with physics education by introducing integrative principles of physics teaching in higher educational institutions, training personnel in new and highly demanded specialties in the education market” was set as a priority task. As a result, pedagogical opportunities for developing logical competence of future physics teachers have expanded.

A number of decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including Decree PD-60 dated January 28, 2022 “On the Development Strategy of New

Uzbekistan for 2022–2026”, Decree PD-5847 dated October 8, 2019 “On approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”, Resolution PR-2909 dated April 20, 2017 “On measures for the further development of the higher education system”, PR-3775 dated June 5, 2018 “On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in the comprehensive reforms being implemented in the country”, Decree PD-5847 dated March 19, 2021. This research work will serve to a certain extent in the implementation of the perspective plans set out in Resolution PR-5032 “On measures to improve the quality of education and develop scientific research in the field of physics” and regulatory documents related to these resolutions and decrees.

The Head of our state Sh.M. Mirziyoyev emphasized: “It is necessary to start reforming the field of science and technology, first of all, with the education of exact and natural sciences. However, during the school period, when the worldview, inventive abilities, tastes, and potential of the emerging younger generation are formed, the most mature, most experienced, and highly logically competent teachers should teach. Therefore, it is planned to radically reform school education, the system of secondary specialized education, and at the same time higher education.”

Theoretical and conceptual approaches to improving the methodology for developing logical competence of future physics teachers, a system of qualities for developing logical competence, and psychological and pedagogical features of organizing a person-centered educational process were identified.

In order to raise the quality of education in the world's educational and research institutions to an international level, to establish modular education, to improve the quality of professional training, future physics teachers should abstract from scientific terms and quantities, relying on logical scientific thinking.

Therefore, the development of competencies in the field of using physics educational experiments should not only be aimed at achieving personal goals, but also be aligned with and suited to the overall objectives of preparing the physics teacher.

METHODS

It is equally obvious to everyone that the knowledge of a mature physics teacher in accordance with the requirements of the time is not enough. There is a need to improve the education system based on a competency-based approach that teaches students to apply acquired knowledge directly in everyday life, and also apply them in the educational process.

The concept of “competence” was first mentioned in scientific literature in the 1950s and 1960s and has not lost its relevance to this day. American scientist Chomsky in his works “Syntactic Structures” [1], “Aspects of Syntax Theory” used competence as a scientific term characterizing a person’s ability to perform any activity. The historical roots of the issues of the competent approach lie in the didactic works of such great thinkers as the Eastern thinkers Abu Rayhan Muhammad ibn Ahmad Al-Beruniy, Abu Nasr Muhammad ibn Muhammad ibn Uzlug Tarkhan Farabiy, Abu Ali Hussein ibn Abdullah ibn al-Hasan ibn Ali ibn Sina, Alisher Navai and in the works of our ancestors, such as Avloniy, Munavvar Kori, Fitrat, many opinions were expressed about the importance and significance of the ideas of competence-oriented knowledge in the development of society.

We pay attention to the interpretation of the concepts and terms “Competence” and “Competency” in dictionaries in order to identify their differences and similarities: Dictionary

meaning of the concept competence is explained in different languages as follows: - Competent (in French) – authorized; - Competent (lat.) – capable; - Competent (in English) – capable.

“Competence (lat. competitive, worthy) 1. The scope of powers of a certain body or official, defined in official documents; power. 2. The level of a person’s awareness in a certain area, knowledge of this area” [2; 396 p.].

In the “National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan” it is interpreted as follows: “competence – knowledge, experience in a particular field” [3; 345 c].

S.I. Ozhegov explains these concepts in the explanatory dictionary of the Russian language as follows: “Competence - 1. Range of issues that a person knows very well or realizes. 2. Scope of human responsibilities and rights.” “Competence is the quality of a person who has deep third-party knowledge in a particular area and is therefore considered reliable and trustworthy” [4; 476 c].

N.A. Muslimov defined competence in the following way: “Competence is expressed in the acquisition of knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for the implementation of personal and socially significant professional activities of students, and their ability to apply them in professional activities” [5; 13 c].

Benjamin Bloom expressed his scientific views on the taxonomy of educational goals. Competence is a term that expresses the level of possession of a set of knowledge that allows one to express true an opinion on a specific issue and represents a generalized set of individual characteristics, the embodiment of knowledge, skills and experience in the same field. Among the definitions and descriptions that shed light on the meaning of competence, the concept of competence is a quality that allows a person to express his opinion on certain issues, participate in the development of certain decisions and make his own decisions. By professional competence in modern science we mean the broad application of the concepts of scientific, managerial, pedagogical, didactic, methodological, and socio-psychological competence.

S. L. Rubinstein asserts that logical actions are comparison, analysis, synthesis, abstraction, generalization in combining different aspects of the main process of thinking, i.e. each side of the main process of thinking. The problem under study is used for objective and subjective analysis, identifying important objective connections and relationships between data, and drawing conclusions. S. Rubinstein describes the process of thinking as a consciously controlled process, the beginning of the thinking process when the need arises to solve a problem defined goals, i.e. conditions, available opportunities, paths, obstacles, developing and studying in detail, contrasting factors, he emphasized that the process of thinking is carried out as a system of intelligent actions with conscious regulation. The examination, criticism and control carried out in this way emphasize the fact that thinking is a conscious process [7, 377 p.].

Analyzing the views of scientists on the process of thinking, they believe that the general aspect of their approach is an effective method of teaching special logical actions for the practical application of theoretically obtained knowledge and information, generalization with manifestation in actions [8, 82 c].

At the end of the 50s of the 20th century, in connection with increasing scientific and technological progress, rapid changes in equipment and production technology, the problem of preparing creative thinking personnel arose. In the field of pedagogy, the search began for ways to develop cognitive abilities, cognitive interests and the ability to independently obtain knowledge

from various sources, observe and conduct experiments for future physics teachers. Currently, the search for new forms of “ Intensive Learning Methods ” and training activities continues.

Figure 1. Basic criteria for the development of logical competence

The main criterion for the development of logical competence is the ability to independently and creatively solve various types of problems, moving from reproductive tasks to creative ones. Famous scientists, didactics and psychologists for several centuries have considered the task of developing the logical competence of students in the educational process to be one of the most important tasks. After studying their research, the main criteria for the development of logical competence were classified as follows (see Figure 1):

In our opinion, the first factor in the formation and development of logical competence is the student's ability to ask questions about physical processes, phenomena and laws. Why? For what purpose? In what sense? What are the consequences? Can there be exceptions to this? By asking questions of themselves and others, they strive to unravel the mysteries of science, and solving these questions is the main criterion of logical competence, which, in turn, gives impetus to further steps[1,2,3,4,5].

RESULT

Our research has shown that the level of development of logical competence of students is very low. The lack of logical literacy often leads to superficial assimilation of academic knowledge by students. This is manifested in the inability to reason based on evidence, the lack of substantiation of conclusions. Each academic subject has elements of logic, but they are not given special attention, so they are not fully used in the educational process.

In the process of reading and learning, a person’s logical competence is gradually formed and developed, in which there are differences in levels of development depending on the environment, quality of educational organization and personality characteristics. In order to assess the level of development of logical competence, it is necessary to formulate certain criterion requirements. Based on the theoretical analysis of the problem under study and work experience, as well as known didactic principles, we have developed general requirements for the development of components of logical competence in the above-mentioned future physics teachers during the lesson:

1. In the process of teaching physics, future physics teachers should become familiar with the laws of formal logic and logical operations, which will allow them to more deeply understand the fundamental essence of the laws of physics, consciously use logical operations and logical laws.

2. All sections of the physics course should be based on the use of the laws of formal logic in the educational process.

3. The use of a system of special tasks and assignments should be aimed at developing the logical thinking of future physics teachers.

4. Lectures, practical classes, use of frontal experimental laboratory classes, organization of independent learning, this type of assignment system should be used in different lessons.

5. When using this systematic approach, it is necessary to determine the level of development of logical competence of future physics teachers, use an individual approach, gradually increase the level of difficulty of tasks, apply rewards and punishments so that students can complete tasks, the personal characteristics of which contribute to mental development.

The components of the logical competence of future physics teachers were classified as follows: analysis-synthesis, comparison, generalization, abstraction, classification, specification, systematization, as well as the ability to apply the principles of formal logic when solving physical problems. These definitions are specific examples explained using.

Figure 2. Components of logical competence of a future physics teacher

Figure 2 provides brief information about the components of logical competence of future physics teachers. Our scientific study, dedicated to the methodology of developing the components of logical competence of future physics teachers, explains in detail the relationship between each component, the components of physical science and logical competence through teaching physics.

DISCUSSION

Based on our scientific research, we have developed general requirements that are most effective in developing the logical competence of future physics teachers in the teaching process:

In the process of teaching physics, students should become familiar with the basics of formal logic, which will allow students to consciously use logical operations and the laws of logic;

Physics teaching based on the use of the laws of formal logic should cover the knowledge of all sections of the physics course, developing students' physical and logical literacy based on the principle of coherence and consistency in the presentation;

In the process of teaching physics, it is necessary to create a system of special tasks and tasks aimed at developing students' logical thinking and to establish their effective use;

It is advisable to improve the methodology for using this type of task system in various practical classes, laboratory classes, independent learning and lecture classes; when using this system, it is necessary to differentiate and individualize the level, that is, to keep credit accounts, to apply incentives and penalties for the complexity of tasks and tasks that contribute to the gradual development of individual characteristics of students, and to assess students as “more knowledgeable than yesterday”.

Pedagogical experience identifies the main components of the system occurring in the process, the goals, tasks, methods, means, conditions, forms, and achievable results in the study of interaction. In addition, along with advanced pedagogical methods, the author's methods “Black box” and “Constructor” were also used. The methodology for developing logical competence in the process of independently acquiring knowledge about physics using literature and didactic materials, the methodology for developing logical competence in organizing independent learning, the methodology for developing logical competence in conducting frontal experiments and performing laboratory work of a research nature, has been improved through the application of the laws of logic and logical operations.

In order to implement the project to develop the logical competence of future physics teachers, the importance of organizing independent learning, lectures, practical and laboratory exercises based on the application of the laws of logic and logical operations was revealed, and the following was organized both online and offline based on the “blended learning” method:

The topic of the lecture lessons, relevant lecture texts, useful literature, electronic resources were provided to future physics teachers in advance through social networks and the “Hemis” system, and future physics teachers familiarized themselves with the main concepts of the topic using the provided resources, prepared notes, and gained an understanding of the topic. During the lecture, future physics teachers learned the logical operations of analysis, synthesis, comparison, contrast, generalization-systemization, classification, and evaluation of the process using the laws of formal logic;

During the practical sessions, future physics teachers performed heuristic tasks and assignments of varying complexity that developed logical competence based on personalized learning, taking into account the individual characteristics of students. With the help of the teacher, new solution methods were found, the results obtained were analyzed and heuristic knowledge was strengthened with real-life examples. Practical lessons were organized using the “Black Box” method as follows: after explaining a new topic, the teacher shows the students a previously prepared box; the students determine the physical properties of the box (mass, size, electrical and magnetic properties, light transmission, etc.) in relation to the lesson topic and express their hypotheses. The teacher explains the correct answer and explains exactly where they made a mistake, and students who actively participated are evaluated. [6,7,8,9,10,11,12].

CONCLUSION

The purpose of the pedagogical experiment was to confirm the research hypothesis: to check the effectiveness of the proposed method for developing the logical competence of a future physics teacher using logical operations based on the laws of logic.

On a scientific and theoretical basis, a methodology has been developed for developing the logical competence of future physics teachers using logic, based on the laws of logic, in teaching physics.

Thus, the results obtained should teach future physics teachers the four basic laws (the law of truth, the law of contradiction, the excluded third law and the law sufficient reason) and logic. Based on the results of scientific and methodological work carried out on the basis of physics concepts, as well as on the application of the acquired knowledge in teaching physics, it would be advisable if the recommendations set out in the article were implemented and effectively contributed to the development of education in our country.

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